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An Assessment of the Experiences of University Teachers on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in classes towards enhanced AI- mediated classes

A Dissertation
Presented to the Faculty of the
Graduate Studies
College of Education, Arts, and Sciences
National University
Manila

In Partial fulfilment of the
Requirements for the degree
Doctor of Education
Major in Educational Management

By:

Wang Feifei

November 2023

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ABSTRACT

Wang Feifei.(2023).*An assessment of the experiences of university teachers on the use of artificial intelligence in classes towards enhanced AI- mediated classes* Manila City. National University. Unpublished doctoral Thesis.

With the advent of fourth-generation information technology, such as cloud computing, big data, and artificial intelligence, higher education has gradually progressed to the stage of intelligent development. Driven by national policies, more and more schools begin to pay attention to artificial intelligence education, purchase artificial intelligence products, establish artificial intelligence studios, build intelligent teaching platforms, etc., but there are still many shortcomings in artificial intelligence education. How should teachers effectively carry out artificial intelligence teaching, and scientific guidance and exploration are urgently needed. This paper takes the intelligent teaching ability of college teachers as the research object, Firstly , understands the research status through literature analysis. Then, based on the theory of stimulus-response learning, the development status of school teachers; teaching ability under artificial intelligence environment was studied through interviews .According to the interview results, teachers can use intelligent tools in classroom design, organization and evaluation to get rid of a lot of tedious work, interact with students better, and improve work efficiency and quality. But there are many challenge of the teachers in AI-mediated classes. Professional knowledge ability and information literacy need to be improved, user information data security needs to be strengthened, and college intelligent teaching and training services need to be provided. In view of these results, this paper puts forward specific strategies to improve teachers' skill in managing AI-mediated class: Establish the concept of AI-3 mediated class; Strengthen data-driven awareness and improve teachers' data literacy; Strengthen the independent development of majors and improve the teachers' skill in managing AI-mediated ;Accelerate the construction of smart campus and provide teacher training opportunities.

Keywords: AI-Mediated Class, Stimulus Response ,Teacher Skill, Teaching ability

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